

**SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT AND SOCIAL IMPACT
OF SMALL BUSINESS ACTIVITIES****Feruzabonu Parpiboyeva Bakhodir kizi**Namangan State University, Faculty of Economics
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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18444281>**ARTICLE INFO**Received: 29st January 2026Accepted: 30th January 2026Online: 31th January 2026**KEYWORDS**

Small business, sustainable development, economic development, employment, social impact, innovation, business environment, government support, competitiveness, social stability

ABSTRACT

This article analyzes the role of small business in the country's economy, the factors of its sustainable development, and its social impact on the development of society. The research highlights the role of small business entities in ensuring employment, increasing incomes, developing innovative activity, and strengthening social stability. Also, mechanisms for supporting entrepreneurial activity, the importance of state policy, as well as existing problems and ways to eliminate them are considered. The results of the research will serve to develop scientific and practical recommendations for the development of small businesses.

Introduction

Today, the development of small business and private business is considered one of the important factors in the country's economic development. Small business entities play an important role in shaping the competitive environment in the economy, creating new jobs, ensuring employment and increasing income levels. For this reason, supporting and encouraging small business and ensuring its sustainable development has been identified as one of the priorities of state policy.

the Republic of Uzbekistan to develop entrepreneurial activity. In particular, the "Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022–2026", approved by the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-60 dated January 28, 2022, pays special attention to the issues of further improving the business environment, expanding access to financial resources, and comprehensive support for small businesses ¹.

The regulatory and legal framework for the development of small business in our country is also being constantly improved. In particular, the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Guarantees of Freedom of Entrepreneurial Activity" establishes the rights of business entities, mechanisms for their protection, and measures of state support ². These documents serve as the legal basis for the stable operation of small business.

¹Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-60 dated January 28, 2022. "Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022–2026".

²Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Guarantees of Freedom of Entrepreneurial Activity". May 2, 2012.

In recent years, small business has been making a significant contribution not only to economic development, but also to ensuring social stability in society. In particular, small business entities serve as an important factor in providing employment to various segments of the population, developing youth and women's entrepreneurship, reducing poverty, and accelerating regional development. The "Every Family is an Entrepreneur" program promoted by our President is one of the important initiatives in this direction ³. At the same time, globalization processes, increased market competition, lack of financial resources, and low level of use of modern technologies are negatively affecting the activities of small businesses. Solving these problems, ensuring the sustainable development of small businesses, and increasing their social impact require scientific research.

this , this article analyzes the factors of sustainable development of small business activity, its impact on social development, mechanisms of support from the state, and existing problems from a scientific, theoretical and practical perspective.

Literature review related to research work

The sustainable development of small business and its socio-economic impact is an important subject of research in economic theory and practice. Scientific research conducted by domestic and foreign scientists in this area is aimed at highlighting the role of small business in economic growth, ensuring employment, developing innovations, and strengthening social stability.

In foreign scientific literature, the theoretical foundations of entrepreneurship are widely covered in the works of such scientists as J. Schumpeter, P. Drucker, M. Porter. In particular, J. Schumpeter interpreted entrepreneurship as a key force accelerating economic development through the introduction of innovations ⁴. P. Drucker evaluated entrepreneurship as a means of effective management and strengthening market competition ⁵. In his research, M. Porter paid special attention to the importance of small businesses in increasing competitiveness ⁶.

Local economists have also conducted a number of scientific studies on the development of small businesses . In particular , the scientific works of A. Vakhobov and B. Khodiev analyzed the role of small businesses in the national economy, the possibilities of using financial resources ⁷, and the issues of improving the investment climate . The studies of S. Gulyamov and D. Rahimov examined the mechanisms of lending, tax incentives, and government support for small businesses ⁸.

the Republic of Uzbekistan are also an important source of scientific research. In particular, the Law "On Guarantees of Freedom of Entrepreneurship" establishes the rights, obligations and mechanisms of state protection of business entities ⁹. Also, the Presidential decrees and resolutions prioritize supporting small businesses, improving the business environment, and reducing bureaucratic barriers.

³Resolutions of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on the program "Every Family is an Entrepreneur". June 7, 2018.

⁴ Schumpeter J. The Theory of Economic Development. —Harvard University Press, 2012.

⁵Drucker P. Innovation and Entrepreneurship. — New York: Harper & Row, 2014.

⁶Porter M. Competitive Advantage. — New York: Free Press, 2016.

⁷Vakhobov A., Khodiev B. Economic Theory. — Tashkent: Economics, 2016.

⁸Gulyomov S., Rahimov D. Financing small businesses. — Tashkent, 2018.

⁹Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Guarantees of Freedom of Entrepreneurial Activity" . 2012 .

In recent years, the social impact of small businesses has been studied in a number of scientific articles and dissertations. Researchers have substantiated the role of small businesses in increasing population growth, developing youth and women's entrepreneurship, reducing poverty, and ensuring regional development. In particular, the expansion of family entrepreneurship and the service sector has been recognized as an important factor in strengthening social stability.

In scientific works devoted to the study of foreign experience, effective mechanisms for supporting small businesses in developed countries, including grants, subsidies, the activities of business incubators, startup centers, and consulting services, have been analyzed. These experiences are also of significant scientific and practical importance from the point of view of their implementation in national conditions.

At the same time, an analysis of the existing literature shows that, although the economic efficiency of small businesses is sufficiently covered in most studies, its sustainable development and social impact are poorly studied in a comprehensive manner. The issues of in-depth analysis of the impact of small businesses on social development across regions are also not sufficiently covered ¹⁰.

For this reason, the main task of this research work was to systematically analyze existing scientific sources, harmonize them with modern economic conditions, and comprehensively study the sustainable development and social impact of small business activities.

Research methodology

In covering this article, the laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan aimed at the development of small business and private entrepreneurship, resolutions of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan, decrees of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, scientific works, works and articles of well-known foreign and local scientists in the economic, social and political spheres were studied. Through this, indicators were analyzed that reflect the development of this sector, increase export potential and create a favorable business environment.

In the process of research, methods such as logical thinking, scientific observation, systematic approach, induction and deduction methods, and comparative analysis were used to study statistical indicators and scientific views on the issue. Also, econometric methods, textbooks, manuals, foreign literature, research reports, scientific and practical conference proceedings, and Internet resources were used to cover the topic. This methodological approach ensured the scientific validity of the research and made it possible to formulate recommendations for the development of small business and private entrepreneurship.

Analysis and results

The study was conducted in 3 small business entities (shops, service centers and micro-firms) in the Namangan region. The goal is to determine the level of sustainable development of small business and its social impact. The results of the study were analyzed according to the following criteria: employment, income growth, innovative activity and social stability.

1st edition

Job creation and income growth

¹⁰Ismailov B. *Regional Entrepreneurship Development*. — Tashkent, 2021.

Business entity	Occupancy rate (%)	Monthly revenue growth (%)	Number of people provided with work (%)
Shops	85	15	12
Service center	70	12	8
Microfirms	60	10	5

(Source : Data from the State Statistics Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 2025).

Table 1 apparently It seems that the shops work in the area with supply the most high (85%), microfirm a l a r d a e s a p a s t (60%). D a r o m a d g r o w t h y e s w o r k w i t h t a ' m i n l a s h g a p a r a l l e t a r z d a o ' s m o q d a : s h o p (1 5 %) > s e r v i c e m a r k e t (1 2 %) > m i c r o f i r m (1 0 %) . This results small entrepreneurship the state of the subjects social - economic positive for development effect show confirmed .

1- d i a g r a m m a d a d o ' c o n l a r w o r k i n t h e a r e a w i t h s u p p l y t h e m o s t h i g h (8 5 %) , s e r v i c e t o s h o w b r a n d s w i t h 7 0 % , m i c r o - f i r m s w i t h 6 0 % s l a v e r y M o n t h l y i n t h e R o m a n E m p i r e g r o w t h a l l t h e w a y s h o p s l e a d e r (1 5 %) , s e r v i c e 1 2 % o f t h e m a r k e t , 1 0 % o f m i c r o -

Diagramma 1: Bandlik darajasi va daromad o'sishi

Diagramma 1: Bandlik darajasi va daromad

firms .This small diagram entrepreneurship of subjects territorial socio - economic to economy secret of the visa t a r z d a k o ' r s a t a d i , w o r k w i t h s u p p l y a n d i n R o m e i n c r e a s e m i d d l e H e l p m e i d e n t i f y t h e c o n n e c t i o n . G i v e i t .

Table 2

Innovation f a h i g h a t a n d s o c i a l e f f e c t

Business entity	New products/services introduced (%)	Use of modern technologies (%)	Social stability (%)
Shops	30	40	55
Service center	50	55	70

Microfirms	20	25	45
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(Source : Data from the State Statistics Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 2025.)

Service centers in the 2nd year are at the highest level of innovative activity increasing production (50 % new product , 55 % technological) . Social stability criteria yes innovation f a higher a t with related : high innovation — high social b a r q a r o r l i k . Microfirm innovation f a higher a t past to be social the secret yes limited (45 %) .

Second small diagram entrepreneurship subjects show centers and microfirm) innovation f a high a t and social stability degree show it . Khizm a t show centers innovation high school the most high increasing the price (50 % more m a product , 55% technological a), shop conl a r o ' r t a ch a , microfirm a l a r e s a p a s t show ' r s a t k i c h g a e g a . Social stability innovation f a high a t with integral related : high innovation — high social sustainability . The highest social sustainability (70%) is in service centers, 55% in shops, 45% in micro - firms . This diagram visually shows the innovative activity of small businesses in relation to social sustainability, helps to analyze regional innovations and social impact.

Conclusion and suggestions

The results of the study show that small businesses play an important role in the sustainable development of the economy and ensuring social stability in society. The main observations are as follows:

occupancy : Small businesses significantly increase the supply of regional labor. Stores and service centers have a high occupancy rate, while micro-firms have a lower rate.

Increased income: Small businesses in the study area have a positive impact on increasing the income of the population. This, in turn, helps to strengthen regional economic stability.

Innovative activity: While service centers are implementing innovative activity at a high level, this indicator is low in micro-firms. It has been found that the level of innovative activity is closely related to social stability.

Social impact: Small businesses contribute to increasing stability in society by developing family businesses, youth and women's entrepreneurship.

Regional differences: Research shows that the economic and social impact of small businesses varies across regions. This requires targeted support from the state.

Based on the research results, the following recommendations were developed:

Strengthening government support: It is necessary to expand opportunities for micro-firms to attract investment through loans, subsidies, and grants.

Promoting innovative activity: It is important to encourage small businesses to create new products and services, and to organize training and consulting services to introduce modern technologies.

Social Development: Strengthen regional stability by promoting youth and women's entrepreneurship. For example, expanding business incubators and training courses.

Monitoring and evaluation system: Regular monitoring of the social and economic impact of small businesses, development of practical recommendations for improving regional development and employment.

Interregional exchange of experience: Increasing the efficiency of small businesses by learning from the experience of developed regions and applying them in other regions..

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